

Selective Extraction of Copper(II) with High Molecular Weight Carboxylic Acid and its Applications

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Comparative extraction behaviour of copper(II) has been performed with high molecular weight carboxylic acids, such as versatic 9, versatic 911, versatic 10 and SRS 100 using benzene as diluent. The effect of pH, extractant concentration, metal ion concentration, diluent and contact time on the extraction of Cu^{2+} have been studied. Copper has been quantitatively extracted at pH 6.0-9.0 with versatic 911 diluted with benzene. The Cu^{2+} : versatic 911 ratio in the extracted species was found to be 1 : 3. Cu^{2+} has been separated from Mg, Ca, Ba, Sr, Mn, Co, Ni, Zn, Cd, Hg, Pb, Al, Fe^{2+} , Cr, Bi and Th. The effect of diverse anions, such as EDTA, thiocyanate, oxalate, thiosulphate, fluoride, iodide, tartrate and bifluoride has been investigated. Quantitative separations of Cu^{2+} from synthetic mixtures have been reported. The proposed method has been applied to extract copper from some of the standard alloy samples.

THERE are several reports in the literature on the extraction of metal ions with carboxylic acids^{1,2}. The typical high molecular weight carboxylic acids, such as versatic 9, versatic 911, versatic 10 and SRS 100 were used in this laboratory for the extraction of di-, tri-, tetra-valent metals³⁻⁶. The composition of the extracted species of several metals using versatic 911 as extractant were investigated by several workers^{6,7}. The present study was undertaken to investigate the extraction behaviour of copper(II) with versatic 911 in benzene. The proposed method is simple, rapid, selective and can be carried out both at micro and macro levels. The method has been applied to extract copper(II) from some of the standard alloy samples. No such study has yet been reported in the literature.

Experimental

Separatory funnels (100 ml) were used for the extraction experiments. The pH measurements were carried out with Ehco LI-10 pH meter.

Versatic 911, versatic 9, versatic 10 and SRS 100 (Shell Chemical, London) were used as such. Versatic 911 is a mixture of saturated tertiary monocarboxylic acids (C_9 , C_{10} and C_{11}) manufactured from C_9 - C_{11} olefins. The concentration and purity of versatic 911 is 5.43 M and 99%, respectively⁷. Versatic 911 was standardised by usual acid-alkalimetric titration. Versatic 9 is a mixture of highly branched saturated aliphatic acids (C_9) while SRS 100 consists of approximately 50% highly branched predominantly tertiary high molecular weight versatic acids (C_{15}) and approximately

50% natural oil. Versatic 10 is a mixture of isomeric tertiary monocarboxylic acids⁸ (C_{10}). These cation-exchangers were suitably diluted in organic solvents and used for the extraction.

CuSO_4 solution (4.95 mg ml^{-1}) was prepared by dissolving $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (AnalaR) in double-deionised water and the solution was standardised by complexometric titration with EDTA (disodium salt) using murexide (murexide-KCl 1 : 100) indicator⁹. Buffer solutions of different pH were prepared from sodium acetate (0.2 M)-acetic acid solution (pH range 3.5-6.75) and from ammonium chloride-ammonium hydroxide solution (pH range 7.0-9.5). All chemicals and solvents used were of analytical grade unless otherwise mentioned.

General procedure of extraction: The aqueous phase was made up of 9.9 mg Cu^{2+} and 10 ml buffer solution. The pH adjustment was done by adding sodium hydroxide solution (pH 3.5-6.75) or ammonia solution (pH 7.0-9.5). The total volume of the aqueous phase was made up to 20 ml, i.e. leaving the ultimate concentration of Cu^{2+} in the aqueous phase $7.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$. The organic phase was prepared from 16.66% versatic 911 in benzene ($9.05 \times 10^{-1} \text{ M}$). The ratio of volumes of aqueous phase and organic phase was maintained at 2 : 1. Both the phases were taken in a separatory funnel and equilibrated. Contact time was varied from 1 to 5 min to achieve maximum extraction. The distribution ratio reached a constant value within 1 min. However, the contact time was maintained at 5 min. The two phases after equilibration were settled for 10 min. Any trace of organic phase left associated with the aqueous phase was washed

with benzene (5 ml). The resulting benzene extract was added to the separated organic phase. The amount of copper in the aqueous phase was estimated by complexometric titration. The organic phase was stripped with 2M HNO₃ (15 ml) for 5 min. The stripped acid extract was neutralised with ammonia and the amount of copper extracted was estimated complexometrically. Variations in procedure are indicated at appropriate places. All the experiments of extraction were carried out at 25 ± 1°.

Results and Discussion

Effect of variables on the extraction :

pH: The extraction behaviour of copper(II) at various pH with versatic 911 is given in Table 1. The experiments were performed at constant extractant (9.05 × 10⁻² M) and metal ion (7.8 × 10⁻³ M) concentrations. The extraction of copper increases with increased pH and becomes quantitative at pH 6.0-9.0.

TABLE 1—EXTRACTION OF Cu⁺⁺ AS A FUNCTION OF VERSATIC 911 AT pH 6.2

Versatic 911 × 10 ⁻¹ M	Extraction %	Distribution ratio (D _{0u})
9.05	100	∞
4.93	100	∞
2.58	100	∞
1.75	97.80	88.9
1.32	95.6	43.45
1.06	94.3	33.08
0.89	89.2	16.52
0.67	78.1	7.13
0.53	64.4	3.62
0.27	22.1	0.57

Versatic 911 concentration : The effect of solvent concentration on extraction was studied by varying the concentration of versatic 911 from 9.05 × 10⁻² to 2.7 × 10⁻³ M using benzene as diluent. The result are given in Table 1. In all the cases, metal ion concentration and pH were kept constant. In case of pure solvent with the increase of pH, the tendency of emulsion formation increases, hence to check it, different dilutions were done for different solvents. As evident from Table 1 the extraction is quantitative for a certain concentration range and then decreases with more dilution of the solvent.

Various diluents : With 9.05 × 10⁻² M versatic solvent in various diluents, the extraction behaviour was tested keeping metal ion concentration, pH (6.2) and volume ratio (2 : 1) constant. Quantitative extraction was obtained with benzene diluent. Hence, the extraction of copper in benzene was preferred for different solvent systems, like versatic 911, versatic 9, versatic 10 and SRS 100.

Different carboxylic acids : The extraction of Cu⁺⁺ at various pH with different carboxylic acids was tested using benzene as diluent. In each case

volume ratio was kept constant. It was observed that of the various solvents (*i.e.* versatic 911, versatic 9, versatic 10 and SRS 100) used, versatic 911 gave the best result. The results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—EXTRACTION OF Cu⁺⁺ WITH DIFFERENT CARBOXYLIC ACIDS AT DIFFERENT pH USING BENZENE DILUENT

pH	Versatic 911	Versatic 9	Versatic 10	SRS 100
4.0	43.4	9.0	10.6	3.2
4.5	73.5	39.5	45.9	15.1
5.0	88.6	81.3	88.2	71.4
5.5	97.8	92.7	96.4	90.3
6.0	99.65	95.2	97	93.3
6.2	99.8	97.3	97.7	95.3
6.5	99.96	99.0	99.0	97.4
7.0	100	100	100	100
7.5	100	100	100	98.7
8.0	100	100	100	93.5
8.5	100	100	100	89.9
9.0	98.1	98.0	96.16	81.3
9.5	70.9	95.6	—	—

Equilibrium time : The contact time was varied from 1 to 5 min. The quantitative extraction was obtained within 1 min and stripping was completed within 3 min. However, contact time for both extraction and stripping were kept 5 min in all the experiments.

Extracted species : The extraction experiments were carried out with constant metal ion concentration (7.8 × 10⁻³ M) at different pH and the corresponding distribution ratios were calculated. The stoichiometry of the extracted species was determined from the result obtained by plotting log D against log [Versatic 911] which produced a straight line of slope 1.53. Shibata and Nishimura⁹ showed that versatic 911 in benzene diluent exists as dimer. Taking into account of this evidence, the extraction mechanism of Cu⁺⁺ is proposed to be

where, the barred species are in the organic phase and R₂H₂ refers to the dimeric form of versatic 911 in benzene solution. The extraction mechanism was further confirmed by plotting log D against pH which produced a straight line of slope 1.94. This indicates the release of two hydrogen ions during extraction which corroborates the proposed stoichiometry of the extracted species.

Extractive separation : The extraction of a definite amount of copper was carried out in presence of varying amounts of diverse ions over the pH range 6.2-7.05. The procedure for extraction was same as described above, except that pH of the solution was adjusted after the addition of diverse ions. Fe⁺⁺⁺, Al, Cr, Cd, Hg and Th interfere under the recommended procedure. Fe, Al, Cr and Th were masked with ammonium bifluoride, and Cd and Hg with potassium iodide. Thus, the interference due to these ions was eliminated. Ca⁺⁺, Mg⁺⁺, Sr⁺⁺, Ba⁺⁺, Co⁺⁺, Ni⁺⁺, Mn⁺⁺,

Zn²⁺, Pb²⁺ and Bi³⁺ do not interfere in the extraction of copper. Iodide, bifluoride, tartrate and thiocyanate do not interfere.

Separation of copper from synthetic mixture: The proposed method was applied for the extraction of copper(II) from some of the synthetic mixtures. Figures in the parenthesis against each ion indicate the amount of the ions present in milligram. The extraction was carried out at pH 6.2 keeping other parameters constant. In most of the cases quantitative extraction was achieved. For the interfering ions, the required amount of masking agents were added before the adjustment of pH. The results are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—QUANTITATIVE SEPARATION OF Cu²⁺ FROM SYNTHETIC MIXTURE

pH = 6.2; Cu ²⁺ = 9.9 mg	
Synthetic mixture (mg)	Cu ²⁺ extracted
Mg(3) + Ca(14)	99.12
Ni(10) + Zn(10)	101.26
Co(10) + Mn(10)	99.24
Ni(10) + Mn(10)	100.63
Zn(10) + Co(10)	100.25
Ni(10) + Co(10)	99.6
*Zn(6) + Cd(10)	100.25
*Al(3) + Ca(14)	98.1
*Al(3) + Bi(3)	101.26
*Zn(6) + Cd(10) + Hg(6)	99.74
Bi(3) + Mg(3) + Ni(10)	99.74
*Al(3) + Mn(6) + Bi(3)	100.75
*Al(3) + Fe(1) + Co(8)	100.25
*Mg(3) + Ca(14) + Sr(13) + Ba(13)	99.62
Mn(6) + Co(6) + Ni(6) + Zn(6)	100

†Cu(NO₃)₂ solution used in place of CuSO₄. *NH₄HF, used for Al, Fe, Cr, and KI for Cd and Hg as masking agents.

Extraction of copper(II) from standard alloys: In order to assess the possible analytical application of the proposed method the recommended procedure was applied for the extraction of Cu²⁺ from some of the standard alloy samples. The alloy samples were dissolved in acids to get the solution and then the proposed procedure was applied for the extraction. In most of the cases quantitative extractions were obtained. The results agree well with the standard data available for the alloy samples (Table 4).

TABLE 4—DETERMINATION OF Cu²⁺ IN ALLOY SAMPLES

Sample	Copper extracted	Certified value	Deviation %
Brass	68.02	67.4	0.92
H. T. Brass 10 G	60.6	60.8	0.33
Aluminium bronze	85.7	85.9	0.23
Copper-nickel 180/2	67.8	68.12	0.47

Process of extraction of Cu²⁺ from alloy samples:

Extraction from brass 5G (Sn + Cu + Pb + Fe + Zn): Brass sample solution was prepared according to the standard procedure. To mask iron, ammonium bifluoride was used and the extractions were carried out at pH 6.55.

Extraction from H.T. brass-10G (Cu + Fe + Sn + Pb + Zn + Al): The analytical procedure of brass was followed for the preparation of solution. A few black particles left insoluble in the solution were filtered through Whatman no. 42 filter paper and washed with hot dilute HNO₃. The volume was made upto 100 ml, and the extraction carried out at pH 6.55 using ammonium bifluoride as masking agent.

Extraction from aluminium bronze (Al + Cu + Fe): The sample (0.557 g) was treated with concentrated HNO₃ (15 ml) and water (10 ml). When vigorous reaction subsided the solution was boiled to 5 ml on a sand-bath, diluted to 50 ml and heated for 20 min to dissolve any insoluble particle left. A clear solution was obtained and the volume made upto 100 ml. Using ammonium bifluoride as masking agent at pH 7.45, quantitative extraction was achieved which agrees well with the standard value.

Extraction from copper-nickel (Cu + Ni + Mn + Fe + S): The solid (0.777 g) was treated with water (10 ml) and concentrated HNO₃ (15 ml). After vigorous reaction ceased it was heated slowly for 5 min giving a clear greenish solution. The volume was made upto 100 ml. The extraction was performed at pH 6.55 using ammonium bifluoride as masking agent.

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